

Urban ReLeaf

Urban ReLeaf Engagement, Communication and Dissemination Plan II

D6.4

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Project Partners

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Acronyms

CoP	Community of Practice
COP28	28th Conference of the Parties (UNFCCC)
CS	Citizen Science
CSO	Civil Society Organisation
DEI	Diversity, Equity and Inclusion
DfB	Design for Business
DG	Directorate-General
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DSIH	Dutch Science Information Hub
ECD	Engagement, Communication and Dissemination
ECS	European Citizen Science
EDI	Equality, Diversity and Inclusion
EEA	European Environment Agency
ECCA	European Climate Change Adaptation
EC	European Commission
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association
ESCT	European Sustainable Cities and Towns
EU	European Union
EURESFO	European Urban Resilience Forum
GA	Grant Agreement
ICC	Intelligent Cities Challenge
EURESFO	European Urban Resilience Forum
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reuseable
GA	General Assembly
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GEO	Group on Earth Observations
GEOSS	Group on Earth Observations System of Systems
ICC	Intelligent Cities Challenge
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
KE	Knowledge Exchange
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NAS	National Adaption Strategy
NAP	National Adaption Plan
NEB	New European Bauhaus
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
PEER	Partnership for European Environmental Research
PURE	Publication and Research (Respository)
QA	Quality Assurance
QC	Quality Control
R&D	Research and Development

RIECS	Research Infrastructure for Environmental Citizen Science
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SEPA	Scottish Environment Protection Agency
SIA	Systems Innovation Approach
SME	Small to Medium Enterprises
STV	Scottish Television
TRH	Temperature, Relative Humidity
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
UKRI	United Kingdom Research and Innovation
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
WOMAD	World of Music, Arts and Dance
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

This document is a deliverable of the Urban ReLeaf project, which is co-funded under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement 101086638 and UKRI Innovate UK grant agreement numbers 10061290 and 10041792.

This deliverable provides an update report on the Engagement, Communication, and Dissemination (ECD) activities carried out during the first half of the Urban ReLeaf project (M1- M28). Building on the initial strategy outlined in Deliverable 6.1, it offers a consolidated overview of outcomes related to engagement events, pilot activities, stakeholder input, communication tools, dissemination activities, and their evaluation through KPIs. The report also documents lessons learned and outlines priorities for the final half of the project.

The revised ECD strategy shifts from awareness-building to action-oriented dissemination, emphasising replication, capacity building, and targeted stakeholder influence. It supports new initiatives including the Accelerator Cities programme; Creativity and Culture Pop-Up Labs; expanded Community of Practice activities; insights workshops; and enhanced support for Key Exploitable Results (KERs). These refinements aim to enhance visibility, enable practical uptake, and ensure lasting impact beyond the project period.

This deliverable comprises 4 parts:

Part 1 - Strategic: the foundation of Urban ReLeaf's ECD activities. It introduces core definitions and the four-phase framework from awareness-raising to post-project sustainability. It presents the "Storytelling for Two" approach, the hub-and-spoke stakeholder outreach model, and alignment with inclusive engagement standards.

Part 2 – Implementation: Engagement Communication and Dissemination. It highlights tools and platforms supporting awareness and participation across six pilot cities in the first 28 months. It covers the evolution of the visual identity, social media, website, stakeholder events, press coverage, audio-visual outputs, dissemination activities, including local city pilot exploitation strategies and broader project innovation action strategies.

Part 3 – Monitoring: Key Performance Indicators. We consolidate the monitoring, metrics and data, reporting against Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), demonstrating engagement across scientific, policy, and public domains, including reach metrics and inclusion progress.

Part 4 - Strategic evolution: next steps for ECD. This is based on lessons learned, outlining shifts toward action-oriented messaging, replication support, and targeted stakeholder influence. It details updated objectives for the final phase (M28–48), emphasising knowledge transfer and accelerator cities support, concluding with post-project sustainability plans.

Introduction

Urban ReLeaf promotes collaboration between local communities and public authorities to address urgent climate issues and support innovations that enable more just and green urban transitions. The project addresses the challenges of increasing environmental stresses in urban areas, accentuated inequalities in access to high-quality greenspace, lack of suitable data for planning and decision making as well as inclusion in public participation in science and research.

The main objectives of Urban ReLeaf are to:

- Understand current data ecosystem and urban greening and participation policies in six pilot cities and co-develop opportunities for citizen science and citizen participation to complement existing practices.
- Mobilise and empower local communities in issues of public interest surrounding urban green infrastructure and environmental stewardship.
- Support the long-term inclusion of active and passive data from citizens within official data streams for urban monitoring, planning and innovation in public policy.
- Encourage knowledge exchange and training across relevant actors beyond the six pilot cities by establishing a community of practice and an accelerator programme.
- Offer flexible and innovative ways of governance that can underpin inclusive green urban planning in support of the European Green Deal and UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

In pursuit of urban climate resilience, six Urban ReLeaf pilot cities co-create participatory, and data-driven innovations to democratise urban greenspace monitoring and the wider policy making process. Athens is undergoing a greening transformation with a new, citizen-powered tree registry providing critical data for better management of greenspaces. Cascais engages citizens in sharing perceptions and thermal comfort levels while using greenspaces to validate the effectiveness of its parks. Meanwhile in Dundee, a city facing increasing grey infrastructure in deprived areas, actions to enhance the accessibility of greenspaces are co-developed with citizens and stakeholders. Mannheim has a heat action plan to safeguard its most vulnerable residents but has identified critical data gaps. Citizen observations of trees and thermal comfort, when integrated with official data streams, will aid the delivery of climate adaptation measures. Riga engages diverse audiences to address concerns about air pollution and greenspace usage, to ensure better informed policies. Finally, in Utrecht, data on temperature, humidity and heat stress, collected by and for citizens, will help them shape effective mitigation strategies to reduce the urban heat island effect.

This mid-term review outlines the activities carried out under the Urban ReLeaf Engagement, Dissemination and Communication (EDC) framework during the first 28 months of the project. It brings together strategic communication objectives, operational dissemination efforts, and engagement actions aligned with Urban ReLeaf's inclusive values, emphasising meaningful and diverse stakeholder participation. More broadly, Work Package 6 (WP6) is cross-cutting and builds on the outputs of all work packages to differing degrees.

This deliverable forms part of WP6: Dissemination, Exploitation and Strategic Communication, which aims to:

- Develop and implement a strategic communications plan to support engagement, knowledge exchange, innovation outputs and dissemination;

- Ensure high-quality brand design to reflect the project's identity and values across all materials; uphold ethical standards, data governance, gender equality, inclusivity, and Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) principles;
- Cultivate strategic relationships with key projects, stakeholders, and networks to maximise visibility;
- Coordinate two Design for Business sprints to drive exploitation of key results.

As the second iteration of the Urban ReLeaf Engagement, Communication and Dissemination Plan, this deliverable offers a midterm reflection on ECD activities (M1–M28), Monitoring of outputs, reach, and lessons learned and a revised strategy and implementation roadmap for the remainder of the project (M28–M48). Specifically, it builds on:

Deliverable 6.1 The Urban ReLeaf strategy and plan for inclusive communication, engagement tools, dissemination, and KPI monitoring <https://zenodo.org/records/7936468>; Deliverable 6.2 which described the first stage visual identity, brand development and website structure, content and launch; Deliverable 6.3 which presented a comprehensive overview of outreach, impact, and exploitation, including pathways to impact through dissemination and initial results.

This report also informs the forthcoming Deliverable 6.5 Cultural & multimedia content, which will present a highly visual report of communications and engagement activity from Urban ReLeaf pilot cities, and, Deliverable 6.6 Outreach, Impact and Exploitation Report II that will explicate the exploitation measures, including intensive dissemination (see section 1.2, Phase 3).

1 Engagement, Communication and Dissemination Strategy

The ECD framework is broken down into engagement efforts across stakeholders, communication campaigns including media presence, and dissemination actions across academic, policy, and practitioner audiences. The planning and execution of the project Engagement, Communication, and Dissemination activities follows a phased schedule closely aligned with key project deliverables and milestones.

1.1 Central Definitions

The terms Communication and Dissemination are in line with the European Commission (EC) definition European Union, 2021, Art. 38). Urban ReLeaf will also engage, build, and maintain a strong relationship with specific actors and audiences throughout the project, with a focus on community empowerment. Therefore, we add engagement as an additional term. As part of the strategy, we have summarised the definition of these terms, first introduced in D6.1 as follows:

Communication

Communication measures to promote the project throughout the full lifespan of the project. The aim is **to inform and reach out to society and show the activities performed, and the use and the benefits the project** will have for citizens. It aims to reach audiences in an inclusive and accessible manner.

Dissemination

The **public disclosure of the results by appropriate means**, other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results, including by scientific publications in any medium.

Engagement

A **process of knowledge exchange** and creation to support co-creation objectives of the project pilots, to encourage and support audiences to become active participants in the project and to foster a sense of ownership and empowerment among participants and communities towards the project. Urban ReLeaf pilot cities will follow and monitor an inclusive engagement strategy to engage a diversity of people.

1.2 Phases

The Urban ReLeaf ECD approach is summarised from D6.1, and structured as follows:

Phase 1 (M1–24): Targeted awareness raising and mobilisation

We established the Urban ReLeaf brand identity, website, and social media channels. Stakeholder mapping identified core audiences and guided the development of a “storytelling for two” communication approach. An inclusive, three-step recruitment process engaged diverse participants, including socially vulnerable groups across all six pilot cities. Early dissemination activities focused on introducing project concepts and methodologies while building relationships and gathering feedback on urban greening policies.

Phase 2 (M13–36): Active Engagement and Visibility

This phase, supported pilot activities through integrated communications, showcasing inclusive community experiences in citizen science campaigns. Each city developed a tailored visual identity and media assets. Communications also helped recruit members for the WP5 Community of Practice Working Groups, exceeding engagement targets. Our messaging aligned with T4.1 Pilot Action Plans, supporting their implementation and iteration as well as WP2 development of pop-up labs approach and commissioning. The development of reels (short videos) and multimedia content aim to further spark interest in environmental monitoring.

Phase 3 (M30–48): Intensive Dissemination

Planning is underway for targeted dissemination, including insight workshops, showcase events in all pilot cities, technical papers for scientific conferences and roadmap for policy, accelerator programme, the toolkit that includes demonstrations of project tools and datasets. This results-focused phase will deploy press strategies and stakeholder outreach to ensure key outcomes reach public, policy, and research audiences before the end of the funding period.

Phase 4 (M48+): Post funding period

Post-project activities will focus on maintaining the website for at least four years, continuing exploitation efforts as outlined in D6.3 and D6.6, responding to EC requests, and identifying opportunities for recognition and scalability of pilot actions. This phase will consolidate impact and support long-term sustainability of project results.

The ECD strategy described in D6.1, developed a **‘hub and spoke’ communication and dissemination model**. The core Urban ReLeaf channels (hub), including the website and centrally managed social media accounts, provide consistent branding and coordination. These are amplified through partner-led dissemination (spokes) through established local-language platforms with long-standing engagement and high trust among target audiences. This model ensures broad outreach of partner organisations.

The Urban ReLeaf consortium has recognised multiple groups who possess an interest in, will benefit from or will be impacted by the project. To effectively reach these audiences, various communication and dissemination efforts, as well as networking and clustering activities, are being implemented. In the first 28 months of the project the channels have been established and as the project is progressing through the different phases the ECD plan is targeting different stakeholder groups accordingly. The updated table 1 outlines stakeholder categories, target audiences and channels that have been instrumental in reaching them.

Table 1: Definition of target stakeholder groups updated with 'hub and spoke' channels

Stakeholder categories	Target Audiences and User Groups	‘Hub and Spoke’ Channels
Academic, Research and Scientific Community	Academic, Research and Scientific user groups, including geography, environmental and data sciences, computing, climate science, earth observation, water, policy and law, engineers, social sciences, design, architecture, and urban planning.	Hub: Urban ReLeaf website, LinkedIn, X, Urban ReLeaf repository Zenodo Spoke: Partners micro-websites, repositories and social media accounts. Conference presentations/webinars.(CoP etc.). Discipline-specific journals (e.g., npj Urban Sustainability).
City Stakeholders	City Councils, municipalities, communities, housing, planning, travel, leisure and parks authorities, public monitoring initiatives, culture, art and design professionals, and intermediary organizations. Open data initiatives, authoritative data agencies, politicians, environmental, NGOs and CSO’s	Hub: Urban ReLeaf website, social media channels, newsletters, data and case studies Spoke: City Pilot micro-websites, Interactive dashboards and open data portals (e.g., digital-twin platforms), ArcGIS Hub, Professional and community interest groups social media channels,
SME’s and Industry	Climate technology, sensor manufacturers, software developers, External data agencies Data-driven innovation Civil engineers, planners, architects.	Hub: Urban ReLeaf website, LinkedIn, X, Urban ReLeaf repository Zenodo Spoke: Partners App Stores (e.g, iOS and Android apps), Datasets
European and international networks, Government and public bodies, and policy makers	Encompassing innovation driven local, regional, national authorities, representatives & associations. National & International Public Administrations, Parliaments. EU standardisation bodies (ISO, CEN-CENELEC, ETSI, etc).	Hub: Urban ReLeaf website, LinkedIn Spoke: Partners data-driven innovation platforms e.g., Utrecht Digital Twin

EU projects and networks working in similar domain	The participation of project partners in other relevant projects offers the opportunity to establish quick links among parties through joint actions e.g., Intelligent Cities Challenge (ICC)	Hub: Urban ReLeaf website, LinkedIn, X, CoP webinars. Partner: policy roundtables, participation via EU projects e.g., Greengage, CitiObs
The general public	A general audience not identified as core to the project, although they can have strong interest: Citizen Interest Groups, NGOs, Community Action Groups, Intermediary Organisations	Hub: Urban ReLeaf website, Instagram, Reels and videos Spoke: Partners Social Media. E.g., Instagram, Facebook, YouTube, Citizen science platforms (EU-Citizen. Science, SciStarter).
Press & Media	Journalists for Local and National newspapers, Industry magazines, and technical, TV stations, local radio, press releases, social media. Influencers	Hub: Website, Press releases and media briefings Spoke: Industry Magazine e.g., Topos, national newspapers (e.g., Die Presse)

1.3 Storytelling for Two Strategy

Urban ReLeaf's 'Storytelling for Two' strategy creates narratives that audiences both connect with and share. Using the "6W" framework (Why, Who, What, When, Where, How), this approach shapes compelling, action-oriented stories across all communication channels. Successfully implemented in pilot campaigns, social media, and community engagement, the strategy ensures messages resonate with diverse stakeholders while building trust and mobilising action. As the project moves into phase 3, this approach will translate complex results into accessible narratives.

1.4 Inclusive Engagement and Green Guidelines

Building on the foundations laid in the initial Engagement, Communication and Dissemination Plan (Deliverable D6.1), Urban ReLeaf is applying an inclusive communication and engagement strategy across all project activities. This strategy is designed to ensure accessibility and participation for a diverse range of individuals, with particular attention to women and vulnerable groups who are often underrepresented and disproportionately affected by environmental hazards.

The inclusive strategy includes specific targets for representation, internal Diversity, Equity and Inclusion (EDI) training, inclusive policy and communications guidance, and a structured, multi-step recruitment approach to support diversity within pilot activities. A monitoring framework is also in place to evaluate demographic reach and inclusivity over time.

Complementing this, Urban ReLeaf's green communication guidelines promote environmentally conscious practices in all communications and events, supporting the project's broader sustainability goals.

2 Communication tools, engagement activities, dissemination and monitoring

2.1 Visual concept and identity

The Urban ReLeaf visual concept and identity were developed in the initial months of the project. The concept and visual tone was developed to adhere to the project values, accessible, approachable, and, authoritative, whilst aligning to the project concepts of grey to green, urban to organic, macro to micro. The aspires to facilitate dissemination activities and ensure consistency in the communication for Urban ReLeaf’s concept, objectives, results, and other outputs.

The project logo, consisting of a logomark and logotype is used consistently across all project communications and dissemination (written deliverables, printed materials, presentations, invitations etc.) to ensure project recognition and visibility. The graphical identity includes fonts, colour palettes, and text directly derived from the project logotype, see Figure 1. For more detailed information on the project graphical identity (see deliverable D6.2).

Since its launch, the identity has been further developed as follows:

- **Motion graphic logo** for film and social media reels.
- **Extended palette** flexibly designed to support bespoke device creation.
- **Spot Illustrations** x 9 to champion the project diversity and inclusion aims.

Figure 1: Urban ReLeaf visual concept and identity, with example spot illustration

2.1.1 Communications resources, templates, training and design

Based on the project visual concept, identity, and communications strategy, several templates and resources were produced. These included: templates for deliverables, PowerPoint presentations (see Figure 2), and project posters (see Figure 3); communications resources and pack; communications training; and design support for pilot cities and dissemination.

A PowerPoint presentation was created and has been adopted and developed as per the needs of project members.

Figure 2: Urban ReLeaf powerpoint template

Project poster templates have been prepared and can be adjusted for different types of outputs.

Figure 3: Urban ReLeaf poster template

Communications Resources (M6 – M48) are provided for project level communication such as flyers, posters, maps (see Figure 4), and pilot-specific assets such as stickers, language-specific banners, image library, and communications planning (see Appendix 3).

ECSA poster design

The ECSA poster features a central map of Europe with callouts to six pilot cities: Utrecht, Riga, Cascais, Dundee, Mannheim, and Athens. Each callout includes a brief description of the city's project. The poster is divided into sections for 'Our Mission', 'Our Objectives', and 'A look at the project in numbers'. The 'Our Objectives' section lists five key goals, and the 'A look at the project in numbers' section provides statistics such as 15 years, 9 countries, €5.2m budget, 15 partners, 6 pilot cities, and 10 accelerator cities. The Urban ReLeaf logo is prominently displayed at the top left.

This A5 card features a map of Europe with callouts to the six pilot cities. It includes the Urban ReLeaf logo, a QR code, and social media handles. The text on the card promotes collaboration between local communities and public authorities to address climate issues related to urban greenspace planning, heat stress, and air pollution in six European cities.

This set of persona cards includes three cards for different roles: Environmental Officer, City Council Member, and Policy Maker. Each card features a placeholder for a photo and a list of interests related to urban heat stress, such as 'Main concerns are interests about heat stress' and 'Main concerns are interests about heat stress'. The cards are designed for use in a gamification activity.

General UR A5 Cards

Persona Cards for Urban Heat Stress Theme Gamification

General UR Poster Map

This poster map features a large map of Europe with callouts to the six pilot cities. It includes the Urban ReLeaf logo, a QR code, and social media handles. The text on the card promotes collaboration between local communities and public authorities to address climate issues related to urban greenspace planning, heat stress, and air pollution in six European cities.

Figure 4: clockwise from from left, Urban ReLeaf ECSA Posters, General UR cards, Persona Cards for Urban Heatstress Gamification, and Urban ReLeaf project map 202

Communications pack (M8) supports the communication and dissemination efforts of partners, including all branding and guidelines (see 3.1), as well as exemplar design assets. It is available on the project Teams repository and on GDrive, the latter gives open access to

named communications employees at city councils and municipalities to facilitate the uptake. It is regularly updated as new assets are created.

Communications Training (M8 – M10) have been provided to all partners, specifically:

- Six workshops, one for each city, were delivered face to face and using Miro collaboration platform to capture inputs. The workshops introduced the good practice for communications, including the ‘Storytelling for two’ strategy (outlined in D6.1) and trained partners in the development of story arcs and key drivers to story sharing. Each city developed and initiated the bespoke storylines and considered target audiences, pilot slogans, and campaign hashtags as well as plotting key milestones (see Figure n).
- Presentations have been given on communications resources, key messages, campaign development, along with engagement insights and updates at consortium meetings, General Assembly 2024, Utrecht and General Assembly 2025, Cascais.

Figure 5: Utrecht exemplar of Pilot City storyarc training and storyline development workshop

Creative Design Request (M10 – M48). In recognition of the importance of consistent, excellent design for communications, a new mechanism to support the uptake of design assets for our 'hub and spoke' model has been set up. This is enabled by a [streamlined design request form](#). The form requires partners to provide dissemination information and edited content e.g., text and high-resolution images, URL's and guidelines, giving a minimum of 3 weeks' notice, ensuring our design team has all necessary materials to deliver quality outputs efficiently.

Bespoke city pilot identities and design assets have been developed to create visuals that are distinct yet aligned with the overall campaign. Custom palettes, graphics, and templates were iteratively created with local input to ensure cultural relevance and visual cohesion across all pilot locations. Selected examples are included in Appendix 1.

2.2 Website

The project website, located at <https://urbanreleaf.eu>, is the central ‘hub’ of our ‘hub and spoke model’. It is a tool and repository for Urban ReLeaf to communicate key project activities, deliverables, and outcomes to an EU- wide audience. The website content undergoes regular updates to both the news section and project outputs.

The regularly updated ‘News’ page, see Figure 6, is primarily aimed at raising visibility, and keeping audiences informed. It is refreshed with longer-form blog-style articles in English and in relevant languages to content and target audience i.e., Dutch, German, Greek, Latvian, Portuguese. News ‘Highlights’ and the most recent articles are also featured on the homepage of the website and are linked to from Urban ReLeaf social media campaigns to attract visitors to read articles. By month 28, we have published 30 News article.

Figure 6: Urban ReLeaf website News section recent articles overview

The articles align to our strategic ‘**Storytelling for Two**’ framework, implementing the six “W” questions: “Why? Who? What? When? Where? hoW?” to guide the development and framing of narratives, as described in Deliverable 6.1. Our Storytelling campaigns have developed around key communications moments for Urban ReLeaf, with targeted use of six ‘W’, that audiences from across all geographic locations can engage with.

The WP6 team develops two main communications campaigns per year, broadly following the development of Urban ReLeaf storylines as they develop over time. In the first 28 months the campaigns have included, City Pilot Introductions, Community of Practice Launch, City Pilot Launch, City Spotlight, and Pilot Next Steps (see Table 2). Additional articles cover and complement key project events, outputs and results.

In line with the success of the approach, the Urban ReLeaf website content will continue to be updated regularly to ensure it encompasses all necessary and up-to-date information regarding the project.

Table 2: Urban ReLeaf articles and campaigns (M4 – 28)

Title	Month	Campaign Name	Targeted '6Ws'
Utrecht's Digital Twin: Advancing Data-Driven Urban Planning	April 2025	Pilot Next Steps	Where + How
Urban ReLeaf Charts Future of Citizen-Led Urban Greening in Cascais	February 2025	Pilot Next Steps	What + When
ReLeaf Cascais: 2024 Campaign Highlights	January 2025	Pilot highlights	What + Where
Athens Enhances Environmental Strategy with Air Quality Sensor Rollout	October 2024	City Spotlight	Who + Why
Volunteers Lead the Way in Dundee's Greenspace Strategy	September 2024	City Spotlight	Where + Why
'Adopt a Sensor' Success: Riga Engages Citizens in Air Quality Monitoring	September 2024	City Spotlight	Where + Why
More Than Measurements: Building Biodiversity and Community in Utrecht	September 2024	City Spotlight	Where + Why
Building a Greener Cascais, 'An Urban Park for the Future' engages more than 300 citizens	September 2024	City Spotlight	Where + Why
Interview with Dr. Rensing, Head of Mannheim's Climate, Nature and Environment Department	September 2024	City Spotlight	Who + Why
'Green Neighbourhood, Cool Neighbourhood' Kicks Off to Tackle Heat Stress in Utrecht	September 2024	City Spotlight	Where + Why
Sunny Celebrations for the Launch of Urban ReLeaf Dundee	August 2024	City Pilot Launch	Where + Why
Mannheim Launches Tree Registry Campaign at the City's First Greening Fair	July 2024	City Pilot Launch	Where + Why
Engaging Communities for Climate Resilience: A Recap of the Urban ReLeaf Workshop at EURESFO 2024	July 2024	Event	How + When

Urban ReLeaf Community of Practice Launch 'Citizen-Powered Innovation'	June 2024	Event	How + Why
Cascais launches "An urban park for the future" campaign	May 2024	City Pilot Launch	Who + Where
Urban ReLeaf General Assembly in Utrecht	April 2024	Event	Who + When
Riga Planning Region Launches 'Adopt a Sensor' Campaign	March 2024	City Pilot Launch	Who + Where
Urban ReLeaf inspired poem at COP28 UAE	December 2023	Event	Why + What
Launching The Urban ReLeaf Blueprint for Inclusive Citizen Engagement	November 2023	Output	What + How
Unveiling the Urban ReLeaf Community of Practice	November 2023	CoP Launch	Why + How
Urban ReLeaf a case study in a New European Bauhaus report	October 2023	Output	Why + What
New report for download 'Pioneering inclusive citizen participation in urban greening policies'	August 2023	Output	What + How
The 'Urban ReLeaf Data Ecosystem Map' for pilot cities	July 2023	Output	What + Where
Adaptive community-based urban planning for the wellbeing of citizens	June 2023	Key Topic Feature	Why + How
Co-creating inclusive strategies for green spaces in Utrecht	June 2023	City Pilot Intros	Where + How
Developing strategies to involve the city's most vulnerable communities in urban greening	June 2023	Output	Who + Why
Creating a greener, liveable and inclusive Dundee	June 2023	City Pilot Intros	Where + Why
Co-creating inclusive strategies for green spaces in Cascais	June 2023	City Pilot Intros	Where + How
Exploring citizen engagement strategies in Athens	June 2023	City Pilot Intros	Where + How
The Urban ReLeaf project kicks off in Laxenburg	June 2023	Event	Who + Why

Partner micro-website project pages which constitute the 'spokes' of our hub and spoke model, have been created to establish project presence, trust and legitimacy using the branded digital infrastructure. These include:

- **APCG** - <http://apcg.meteo.noa.gr/index.php/news-events/189-kicking-off-our-new-horizon-europe-urbanreleaf>

- **Cascais Ambiente** - Project page <https://data.cascais.pt/geral/urban-releaf>
- **I-SENSE (ICCS) Group** - i-sense.iccs.gr/projects/urban-releaf
- **ICLEI Europe** - [project page](#) on the main website
- **IIASA** - iiasa.ac.at/projects/urban-releaf-citizen-powered-data-ecosystems-for-inclusive-and-green-urban-transitions
- **Mannheim** - <https://www.mannheim.de/de/urbanreleaf>
- **Smart Riga** - smartriga.lv/projects_cases/urban-releaf-citizen-powered-data-ecosystems-for-inclusive-and-green-urban-transitions/
- **Sustainable Dundee** - Dundee City Council project page sustainabledundee.co.uk/projects/urban-releaf
- **University of Dundee** - Project page <https://dundee.ac.uk/projects/urban-releaf>
- **Utrecht** - <https://samenmetenutrecht.nl/project/koele-buurt/>
- **VUB** - https://researchportal.vub.be/en/projects/urban-releaf-citizen-powered-data-ecosystems-for-inclusive-and-gr?utm_source=chatgpt.com

Additionally, Urban ReLeaf is promoted on the following platforms:

- **SciStarter** - listing on the SciStarter platform, access [here](#)
- **European Citizen Science Platform** - Provides an overview of the project goals and partners, access [here](#)

2.3 Social Media Presence

Urban ReLeaf social media activities directly support WP6 objectives by raising awareness of the project activities among key stakeholders, facilitating knowledge transfer between pilot cities, and building a community of practice around urban greening strategies.

Since month 4, Urban ReLeaf has maintained active project 'Hub' platforms LinkedIn, Instagram, and X (formally Twitter) accounts, recognising social media's crucial role in outreach. UNIVDUN manages these platforms, providing regular updates on consortium workshops, city pilot activities, dissemination of results and cross-platform campaigns.

Through collaborating with all partners, we ensure content accurately reflects all contributions to Urban ReLeaf activities. Additionally, the project follows relevant initiatives and accounts that may serve as Urban ReLeaf ambassadors, helping expand the project's social media reach.

Each platform employs a differentiated content strategy to maximise engagement and reflecting the different audiences they attract.

- **LinkedIn** focuses on professional and academic updates, targeting city councils, researchers, practitioners and policymakers.
- **Instagram** showcases visual documentation of pilot sites and community engagement activities to reach local stakeholders and citizens.
- **X** focuses on time-sensitive announcements and project conversations, reaching an audience similar to LinkedIn.

The project has developed a consistent hashtag strategy applied by partners to support monitoring, increase content discoverability and connect with relevant communities of practice #UrbanDesign, #CitizenScience #Inclusion and #NatureBasedSolutions

Secondary hashtags include #greendeal, #SDG11, #climateaction #greenspace #greeninfrastructure, as well as post-specific tags where appropriate to boost exposure.

We use #ReLeafCities consistently across all platforms to enable tracking of partner produced content, and create pilot-specific hashtags (e.g., #ReLeafUtrecht) for localised activities.

Graphics and design are also key to visibility and engagement click through rates, across social media platforms, selected examples are included in Appendix 3.

Urban ReLeaf enhances its reach through coordinating social media through partner accounts. This cross-promotion approach, means consortium partners regularly share and amplify project content through their organisational and individual social media accounts in local languages. The content is supported by Urban ReLeaf design services, including for graphics and short reels. This expands visibility across diverse professional networks and geographical regions.

2.3.1 Press Releases and Media Coverage

Press releases are regularly published by all partners, highlighting content relevant to the main achievements or significant events occurring during each respective period. Through the dissemination of press releases the project ensures transparent and comprehensive communication, fostering engagement and awareness among its audience.

Highlighted press releases and media activities include:

Riga Press Coverage on Air Pollution Sensor Launch, 23 Oct 2024, Coverage across 3 national media outlets (print + online) reaching the general public

IIASA Press Feature in “Die Presse” on 5 Apr 2025, National newspaper interview on sensors and Urban ReLeaf reaching Media (Press Release), policymakers and the general public

Green Neighbourhood Cool Neighbourhood (Utrecht) Press release promoted external visibility of pilot milestones and results

Topos Magazine 127 ‘Heat’ article ‘Heat City Game Changers’ by Anna Martin, presented Urban ReLeaf, see Figure 15. Topos magazine is the leading international and interdisciplinary review for landscape architecture, urban design and urban development.

Figure 7: Topos Magazine 127, front cover, contents and article 'City Game Changers'

Television broadcast on **STV News** on 7 March 2021, see Figure 16, featured the Dundee pilot, introduced Urban ReLeaf’s citizen science approach and highlighted upcoming opportunities for community involvement in environmental monitoring. The segment included interviews with Mel Woods (University of Dundee) and a representative from Andrew Llanwarne (Friends of the Earth Tayside), offering local perspectives on climate action and urban greening initiatives. [Recording on file; not publicly available].

Figure 8: STV News, UK, segment from 7 March 2021

2.4 Stakeholder Engagement

The initial stakeholder mapping from Deliverable 6.1 outlines key engagement activities with stakeholders across the pilot cities, including citizens, community organisations, policy actors, and research partners. Engagement formats include participatory workshops, co-design labs, seasonal campaigns, community events, scientific festivals, and public data-gathering activities, tailored to each pilot city’s context and target groups (see D6.1, section 1.3.1: Stakeholder mapping for further details)

2.5 Inclusive engagement and green guidelines

Urban ReLeaf is committed to ensuring that design, events and communications meet highest ethical standards, data governance principles, gender equality and inclusiveness values, and RRI guidelines more generally. Therefore, on a regular basis, the Inclusivity, Diversity and Equity manager of the Urban ReLeaf project, being Carina Veeckman from VUB, provides strategic advice to the six cities for setting up local engagement strategies (e.g. during monthly check-ins) – in collaboration with WP4 manager IIASA. In specific, the identification of target groups is discussed, as well as their specific profiles, motivations, barriers and tactics of how to recruit and engage them into the project’s activities. During the pilots’ implementation, an inclusivity monitoring process is set up which tracks all the engagement activities and the diversity of the profiles. The inclusivity monitoring makes sure that Urban ReLeaf engages diverse profiles in the project and supports the distribution of epistemic authority. In practice, participants are invited, on a voluntarily basis, to provide a few socio-demographic characteristics (age, gender and education level) during the registration process for reaching the inclusivity targets of the project.

Overall, for engaging participants, the pilot cities attain a three-step recruitment process:

Step I: open call	Step II: Inclusion criteria	Step III: targeted approach
General call via (social media), newsletters, public website to join the Urban ReLeaf project	Monitoring the demographic characteristics of the recruited participants from step I	If necessary, personal invitations and collaborations through partnerships and intermediary networks to recruit missing profiles

2.6 Engagement Events

As part of the Urban ReLeaf project's comprehensive engagement strategy, a series of events have been organised or co-organised to facilitate project activities, connect with stakeholders, and support collaboration across the pilot cities and beyond. An overview of these can be found in table 7 below, with a summary of metrics associated with participation in city pilots found in figure 18, and an update on KPIs in section 3. These events have played a critical role in engaging local communities, policymakers, and academic networks.

Table 3: Overview of engagement events, locations and stakeholder types

Event Name	Type	Date(s)	Location	Audience	Notes
Cascais Urban ReLeaf Campaign Events (series)	Community Campaign	2023–2025	Cascais, PT	Citizens, youth, general public	Seasonal campaign events with strong youth/public outreach
Dundee Stakeholder Workshops (Series)	Community events and workshops	2023 - 25	Dundee, UK	Citizens, NGOs, local gov	Hands on engagement with apps
DSIH Citizen Science Magazine + Video Launch	Media campaign + event	Jan 2024	Utrecht, NL (online)	General public, CS community	Creative media to explain citizen science >1,000 (online)
ECISA Workshop: Diversity and Inclusivity in Citizen Science	Workshop	Apr 2024	Vienna, AT	Researchers, NGOs	~20
Creative Days Vienna - Urban Innovation Session	Workshop	May 2024	Vienna, AT	Urban planners, creatives, researchers	~30
Future Green City World Congress	Conference + workshop	Sept 2024	Utrecht, NL	Cities, researchers, policymakers, public	>300
Utrecht Together Measuring Festival	Conference	Oct 2024	Utrecht, NL	Citizens, scientists, urban planners	Large-scale public engagement on urban measurement >150
Climate Neutrality & Resilient Athens Conference	Conference	Feb 2025	Athens, GR	Civil society, media, gov, public	~100

Across these events, Urban ReLeaf has directly engaged stakeholders across our target groups, spanning citizens, policymakers, researchers, and NGOs. Events have successfully created dialogue across sectors and stimulated knowledge exchange, with creative formats (e.g., festivals, community events and competitions) proving particularly effective in public engagement.

2.7 Dissemination

The strategic approach to dissemination is defined here as the targeted sharing of project results with stakeholders who can use or build upon them, including policymakers, researchers, CS practitioners, and institutions. Dissemination supports project visibility, uptake, and long-term sustainability, and is closely linked with communication and exploitation.

Urban ReLeaf is maximising the visibility and impact of our outputs and results, while also ensuring that they are accessible and understandable to a diverse audience. A dissemination log (see Appendix 1) is regularly updated by all partners, typically activities include outputs and results conveyed through scientific & policy dissemination (e.g., conferences, briefs, reports) (see table n.). This includes a calendar and planner which is regularly updated and includes targeted dissemination opportunities to reach key stakeholders e.g., conferences, workshops, journals and competitions.

In addition to the project website, Urban ReLeaf infrastructure includes the following repositories and access portals:

- **Zenodo** open-access repository, All Urban ReLeaf project deliverables and outputs are deposited <https://zenodo.org/communities/urbanreleaf>
- **Institutional open access repositories** such as PURE for outputs, which include DOIs to ensure persistent access and citability e.g., IIASA, VUB, UNIVDUN.
- **ORCID** for named researchers for dissemination of results.

The consortium is actively engaging in partnership working, ensuring strong collaborative relationships between consortium partners, alignment with other EU-funded initiatives, as well as external initiatives and actors. These partnerships underpin the co-creation of tools and outputs, shared results and insights. A culture of mutual learning has been cultivated through regular exchanges, workshops, and communication activities.

2.7.1 Dissemination Activities

A cross-section of dissemination activities and events across different formats have been undertaken in the first 28 months. Table 8. shows a selection along with their type, location, target audience, and information including participation metrics, where known. The full dissemination log is available in Appendix 1.

These efforts have been crucial in facilitating the uptake of the projects outputs across target stakeholders.

Table 4: Example dissemination activities, location, audience and details (M1–28)

Output / Event	Type	Date	Location	Audience	Notes
10th European Urban Resilience Forum (EURESFO)	Conference	Oct 2023	Cascais, PT	International policy and science audience	Two sessions on climate data innovation and CoP >200

CitiObs Mutual Learning Workshop	Workshop	Jan 2024	Athens, GR	EU project peers, policy makers	Cross-project learning among Horizon consortia ~30
The New European Bauhaus at the local and regional level	Policy report	2024	Urban ReLeaf website and Publications office of EU	EU project peers, Local Authorities, policy makers	Showcased the contribution of local authorities to the NEB Mannheim pilot as case study
Creative Days Vienna – Urban Innovation Session	Workshop	May 2024	Vienna, AT	Urban planners, creatives, researchers	~30
I-Tree Conference	Conference, presentation + workshop	June 2024	Dundee, UK	Urban planners, policymakers, local gov, academics	Urban ReLeaf plenary day, presentations and workshop ~300
Future Green City World Congress	Conference + Workshop	Sept 2024	Utrecht, NL	Cities, researchers, policymakers, public	>300
Climate Neutrality & Resilient Athens Conference	Conference	Feb 2025	Athens, GR	Civil society, media, gov, public	~100 (est.)
IIASA at Dresden Nexus Conference	Presentation	Apr 2025	Dresden, DE	Academics, policy, NGOs	~30

We also share key results across through online channels and using storylines. A recent round-up Campaign insights from 2024 was created to celebrate the achievements of city pilots, this was designed as mixed-media infographic for broad appeal, as seen in figure 18.

2.8 Audio Visual Outputs

The project is committed to producing high-quality videos to document the pilot city experiences and results through the perspectives of participating citizens, communities, and other actors. These employ a documentary-style format to illustrate the project's progress over time and highlight key milestones and achievements.

The first output, a project poem and video, was produced in collaboration with *Hot Poets International*. Titled '**Super Sleuths of the Streets**' it is a poem that imagines the Urban ReLeaf project 10 years into the future. It's aim is to showcase a hopeful citizens perspective

of Urban ReLeaf's six pioneering cities, Athens, Cascais, Dundee, Mannheim, Riga, and Utrecht.

The output is recorded as a video, with drone footage supplied by Urban ReLeaf Cities, see Figure 17, and the poem it has also been performed live in various venues.

Figure 9: Super Sleuths of the Streets video stills

'**Super Sleuths of the Streets**' video has been viewed over 2,000 times across various online platforms, including [Hot Poets YouTube](#), streamed on EcoFlix, and widely shared on Urban ReLeaf social media. The poem and video was screened at the [Detroit Better Cities Festival 2024](#), and has been featured throughout 2024 and 2025 through the 'Better Cities' satellite screening events, globally.

Poet Liv Torc has also performed the poem live at prestigious events and festivals, including:

- COP28, UNFCCC Resilience Frontiers COP28 programme, Dubai
- *Poetry, Science & Saving the World*, University of Oxford / Natural History Museum, 2024, UK
- WOMAD 2024 Festival, UK

Additionally, we have created a number of videos, vox pops and reels available on YouTube and on social media, to disseminate and present the project activities and results, these include:

Project Videos and Reels (Instagram and LinkedIn)

- Cascais 2025 General Assembly overview, access [here](#)
- Sustainable Celebrations for the Urban ReLeaf Pilot Cities, access [here](#)
- Urban ReLeaf Dundee launch, access [here](#)
- Utrecht 2025 General Assembly overview, access [here](#)
- World Cities Day campaign promoted a youth response to the following questions:
 - Young volunteers from Cascais answering the question '*What inspired you to join Urban ReLeaf and get involved in local climate action?*'
 - Young people from Mannheim, Riga and Dundee shared their thoughts and visions for sustainable cities and resilient futures, '*How does climate change impact young lives?*' Access [here](#)

City Pilot videos

- Cascais (Cascais Municipality, 2024) invites residents to participate in assessing and enhancing the comfort and resilience of Cascais' urban green areas, access [here](#)
- Sustainable Dundee (Dundee City Council, 2024), Dundee City Council's city leader invites residents to take part in the pilot campaign, access [here](#)

2.9 Awards and Competitions Submissions

Competitions and awards are a valuable part of Urban ReLeaf’s dissemination strategy. These external-facing opportunities showcase project innovations, results, or narratives to wider audiences including experts, media, and the general public. They not only amplify visibility but also validate the project through peer review and through international dialogues on urban resilience, citizen science, and participatory approaches.

As part of this effort, Urban ReLeaf’s short film “Super Sleuths of the Streets” was selected and shortlisted for the [Detroit Better Cities Festival](#) 2025 (see section 3.8). The Better Cities Film Festival collects, curates, and presents impactful films that explore themes of improving cities, towns, and neighbourhoods.

The project made a formal submission to the [EU Citizen Science Prize 2025](#), a Europe-wide call for innovative approaches to citizen engagement and environmental sensing. A mixed-media infographic for social media was developed to support the application, showcasing how Urban ReLeaf combines storytelling, community science, and digital tools (Figure 18).

Figure 10: Mixed media infographics with key metrics for pilot city campaign impacts and insights 2024

2.10 Dissemination - Exploitation Interface

Dissemination is inherently connected and linked with exploitation. The key difference is that whilst dissemination makes the project's results visible to wider audiences and targets stakeholders, exploitation ensures its outcomes are effectively utilised, as an ongoing endeavour, both during and beyond project implementation. Nevertheless, it is important to highlight the specific overlap between these two activities and the implication for planning for communication and dissemination.

We develop a comprehensive plan that includes clear objectives, target audiences, content creation, dissemination channels, for the exploitation of outputs. The Urban ReLeaf exploitation plan (D6.3) identified 17 key exploitable results (KERs¹). The communication plan supports the exploitation of several of these KER as outlined in Table 9.

Table 5: Key exploitable results, audiences and dissemination measures

Key Exploitable Result	Target Audience / Stakeholder	Dissemination Measures relevant for Exploitation
Strategy blueprints for Inclusive Citizen Science (D2.2)	Academic and Research Policy makers, practitioner and researchers	Academic publication Promotion through posters, infographics and presentations at events Upload to Zenodo and Urban ReLeaf website, promotion through LinkedIn and core channels.
Best Practices for Inclusive Culture and Community Pop-Up Labs (D2.3)	Research/academic institutions, policymakers.	Science/policy practice dissemination events. <i>Academic paper in <i>Humanities & Social Sciences Communications</i> or <i>Citizen Science Theory and Practice</i>.</i> Upload to Zenodo and Urban ReLeaf website, communications through LinkedIn
Tree Canopy Map (D3.4, 3.8)	Copernicus teams, urban planners, greenspace planners.	Communication on the availability of the data and connecting with possible end-users through LinkedIn. Branding, graphical and visualisation support.
Participatory Tree Register Application (D3.5)	Research Institutes	Planned Publications DOI assignation Branding, graphical and visualisation support
Urban ReLeaf Perceptions Application (D3.5)	Research Institutes, CSOs	Journal publication. Integration in suite of Geo-Wiki tools.

¹ Defined as tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature' which have been deemed to be of high priority for project transfer actions.

		<p>Upload to Zenodo and Urban ReLeaf website, communications through LinkedIn</p> <p>Branding, graphical and visualisation support</p>
TRH Sensors & EcoPulse Mobile Application/ web platform (D3.6)	Public Authorities, Research Institutes, Health Agencies	<p>Presentations at conferences, and possible publications.</p> <p>Branding, graphical and visualisation support</p>
Guidelines for QA/QC in Citizen Science Data (D3.7)	CS technology users, research institutions, local authorities	<p>CoP – to communicate and disseminate the guidelines.</p> <p>Dissemination via EU CS networks, sister projects and wider networks.</p> <p>Upload to Zenodo and Urban ReLeaf website, communications through LinkedIn</p>
Evaluation/Impact Framework & Impact Briefs (D4.10)	Policymakers, researchers	<p>Dissemination in Horizon Europe networks and relevant conferences.</p> <p>Journal publication.</p> <p>Upload to Zenodo and Urban ReLeaf website, communications through LinkedIn</p>
Innovative Governance Models for Pilot Cities (D5.2)	Local and EU policymakers, urban planners, municipalities.	<p>CoP – A key exploitation activity to connect results with potential end users, supported by policy briefs and published through ICLEI channels.</p> <p>Policy recommendation document, presented at relevant events such as EURESFO, ESCT Conference, ECCA, or similar.</p> <p>Upload to Zenodo and Urban ReLeaf website, communications through LinkedIn</p>
Urban ReLeaf Toolkit (D5.3)	CSOs, CS practitioners and researchers, higher education institutions.	<p>Launch campaign.</p> <p>Presenting at EU events and other relevant academic venues.</p> <p>Disseminate and upload to relevant online toolkit platforms and indexes.</p> <p>Upload to Zenodo and Urban ReLeaf website, communications through LinkedIn</p>
Urban ReLeaf Adoption Roadmap (D5.3)	Policymakers, researchers, citizen science practitioners	<p>Launch campaign.</p> <p>Dissemination in Horizon Europe networks and relevant conferences.</p> <p>Journal publication.</p>

		Upload to Zenodo and Urban ReLeaf website, communications through LinkedIn
Storytelling Strategy & Framework (D6.1)	Policymakers, research community, professional project teams	<p>Multimedia content, storytelling workshops to raise awareness of this approach.</p> <p>Journal publication. Strategy and guidance for storytelling for different stakeholder groups e.g. citizens, policy-makers.</p> <p>Upload to Zenodo and Urban ReLeaf website, communications through LinkedIn</p>

The outlined dissemination activities provide a critical link in the wider pathway to impact through their contribution as exploitation measures. In addition to the specific measures outlined above, the planned production of final report of key results, will form an important communication and dissemination task to support the collective exploitation of the KERs. Further details of Urban ReLeaf’s exploitation activities can be found in Deliverable 6.3: Urban ReLeaf outreach, impact and exploitation report I.

AWAITING VALIDATION BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

3 Monitoring, Evaluation, KPIs

This section outlines how the ECD strategy was monitored and evaluated through pre-defined Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). It presents a summary of metrics, data collection methods, and how performance aligned with the expected targets for M1–M28 across the Urban ReLeaf website, Social Media, Inclusion Targets

Summary highlights:

- 20+ events hosted or co-organised.
- 50,000+ visits through the online presence, including Website and Social Media
- 15+ dissemination materials published.
- Increased inclusion of vulnerable and marginalised groups through participation at events reported through the dissemination log (WP6, UNIDUN), and an analysis of inclusion metrics, based on structured pilot monitoring as part of (WP2, VUB)

3.1 Progress against the KPIs

For measuring effectiveness, the following KPIs and related numbers have been foreseen in the Description of Action in relation to WP6. These targets are either delivered or supported through monitoring of communications and engagement as part of the engagement, communication and dissemination plan (Table 10).

Table 6: Selected Key Performance Indicators and targets

KPI	Description	Target	Status
1	No. of citizens to be mobilised	250 -1500/city	N/A On track
2	No. of cities to be recruited through accelerator programme	10	N/A On track
3	Minimum share of women participants in campaigns	50%	In progress
4	Share of participants from vulnerable/marginalized groups across city pilots	30-40%	In progress
9	No. of stakeholders participating in co-design workshops	75-120 total; 12-20/city	Achieved
14	No. of participants in Design for Business sprints, Pop-up community and culture labs	DfB:20-30/city; Pop-up Labs 30-40/city	N/A On track
20	No. of visitors to Urban ReLeaf online presence & social media	Y1: 10,000+; Y2: 50,000+; Y3: 100,000+; Y4: 200,000+;	Y1: Achieved Y2: Achieved Y3: On track

The matrix, see table 11, below, illustrates the breadth of Urban ReLeaf's audience engagement and dissemination during the first 28 months of the project. This matrix complements the KPI data by showing the diversity of engagement types and broad communication activities (from social media campaigns to the website and open data tools) in

alignment to the project’s key audiences. This is presented to demonstrate the progress against our multi-stakeholder objectives.,

Each checkmark (✓) indicates a single activity that is targeted at the given engagement type and stakeholder group, multiple checkmarks indicate multiple activities in the category.

Table 7: Stakeholder Reach Matrix

Engagement Type	Scientific	Civil Society	Policy Makers	General Public	Media
Social Media Campaigns	✓	✓✓✓✓✓	✓✓	✓✓✓✓✓	✓✓
Public Workshops	✓	✓✓✓✓	✓✓	✓✓✓✓	
Conference Presentations	✓✓✓		✓		
Policy Briefings & Webinars	✓✓	✓	✓✓✓		
Press & Media Engagement		✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓✓✓
Storytelling & Creative Projects	✓	✓✓✓✓	✓	✓✓	
Website & Open Data Tools	✓✓	✓✓	✓	✓✓✓	

The evaluation of the KPIs from the first 28 months is a summary, following on we unpack the communication and dissemination monitoring for Urban ReLeaf in more detail.

3.2 Urban ReLeaf Website Monitoring

The impact of the website is monitored using Siteimprove. In the period from April 2023 to April 2025, the website was visited by 4115 discreet visitors, with 5502 page views and an average visit duration of 2.11 minutes.

The Urban ReLeaf website has garnered significant international attention, with visitors primarily from Europe but extending across 102 countries worldwide, see Figure 7, demonstrating the global relevance of the project's aims. While the United Kingdom, Austria, The Netherlands, Germany, Greece, Portugal, and Belgium represent the primary sources of website traffic, almost one quarter of reach highlights the broad interest in Urban ReLeaf's approach.

Figure 11: Urban ReLeaf website visitors by country pie chart

The most visited pages, after the Homepage, are the pages About the project concept, aims and objectives, the page describing Pilot cities, the News section and Outputs, illustrated in Figure 8.

Figure 12: Urban ReLeaf website Top 10 pages overview

Social Media Monitoring

We have implemented a systematic approach to track Urban ReLeaf's social media performance across all platforms within our 'Hub and Spoke' model. This includes monitoring both core project channels and partner networks. Monthly engagement

metrics are compiled using a standardised spreadsheet that captures key performance indicators i.e., impressions, likes, comments, shares, and follower growth. Quarterly analysis identifies the content and themes generating the highest engagement levels. These performance insights are shared regularly with consortium partners during project meetings and annual general assemblies. This data-driven approach enables continuous refinements to our social media strategy while ensuring communication efforts remain aligned with overall project objectives.

Due to differences in how social media platforms categorise and label engagement metrics, direct comparisons can be challenging. To facilitate KPI reporting, we align comparative terms to standardise metrics across channels. This approach enables cross-platform performance analysis and helps identify which content types generate the most engagement across different stakeholder groups, as follows:

- **‘Views’ and ‘Impressions’** Treated as equivalent metrics representing content visibility.
- **‘Engagements’, ‘Likes’, and ‘Interactions’** Grouped together as basic engagement indicators.
- **‘Comments’ and ‘Reposts’** Identified as high-value engagement metrics representing deeper audience connection and active amplification.

The hierarchy reflects the increasing levels of audience investment, with more passive ‘views’ requiring minimal effort, and ‘commenting’ or ‘reposts’ demonstrating substantial engagement and willingness to associate with the project content.

Table 3 below shows a simplified comparison, we acknowledge that platform-specific nuances may still influence interpretation.

Table 8: Overview of social media performance [as of M28]

Platform	Followers	Views / Impressions	Likes / Engagements / Interactions	Comments	Reposts
LinkedIn	914	44,009	10,236	141	397
Instagram	180	8,386	1963	56	n/a
X	132	43,655	1523	41	207
Total	1,226	96,050	13,722	187	604

The following sub-sections unpack the content and engagement across the multiple Urban ReLeaf social media channels.

3.2.1 Urban ReLeaf LinkedIn

Figure 13: Urban ReLeaf LinkedIn page showing followers at Month 28

The Urban ReLeaf LinkedIn page has grown to 912 followers between months 4 and 28 of the project (see Figure 9.), with a significant increase from 546 followers over the past 12 months. Similarly, the engagement performance metrics have increased. The content is tailored to a professional audience and showcases a variety of activities, including project updates, pilot city initiatives, dissemination of research findings, event highlights, and key partner achievements.

Content that highlights major project announcements relevant to all partners, such as launch activities, tend to perform better than announcements of upcoming specialist activities e.g., conferences. Community-focused initiatives, such as Dundee's Greenspace Strategy, and expert features involving notable policy or environmental figures, such as the Mannheim Interview with Dr. Rensing, also generate strong engagement. Timely, visually appealing content tied to significant dates such as World Earth Day, have proven effective in capturing audience interest (see Table 4.).

Audience analysis reveals that most visitors are engaged in research (24.2%), business development (9.3%), and community services (8.7%). The dominant job functions are research (14.4%) and education (10.6%), suggesting a strong academic and professional following. Geographically, the majority of visitors come from Vienna, Austria (11.4%), Dundee, UK, (9.1%), and the Randstad region in the Netherlands (5.6%).

Table 9: Top Performing LinkedIn Content (M4 – 28)

LinkedIn Post Title / Content	View / Impressions	Likes / Engagements / Interactions	Engagement Rate
Mannheim Interview with Dr. Rensing	2,045	1,042	28%
Dundee’s Greenspace Strategy	1,798	771	23%
World Earth Day 2024	1,627	N/A	6.3%
Dundee Pilot Launch	1,616	1126	37%

Due to limitations on dashboard service and data analytics for LinkedIn standard accounts, we can only display graph data for the most recent 12-month period, however, the total follower count is visible, as shown in Figure 10, below.

Figure 14: LinkedIn page followers metrics and graph (M18 – 28)

Apr 22, 2024 - Apr 19, 2025 ▾
Export

Your profile view highlights

Data for 4/22/2024 - 4/19/2025

34,375

Impressions

1,268

Reactions

26

Comments

41

Reposts

Metrics

Impressions ▾

Figure 15: LinkedIn page engagement metrics and graph (M18 – 28)

LinkedIn Insights

There is a notable need to improve visibility and engagement for pilot cities that have lower follower counts, these cities do not have an active organisational presence on LinkedIn, namely Riga (5 followers) and Mannheim (10 followers). In the remainder of the project we will look to strengthen their presence to achieve more balanced representation across the pilots. Specifically these will target the following:

- **Posts focusing on community efforts** e.g., Dundee's Greenspace Strategy generate considerable local interest.
- **Content with expert insights** or features with social and environmental figures (e.g., Mannheim interview, Utrecht Digital Twin) drive significant engagement.
- **Visual and timely posts**, such as those for Earth Day, perform well.
- **Pilot cities** with official social media platforms generate more engagement overall than those without e.g., Riga and Mannheim.

3.2.2 Urban ReLeaf Instagram

Figure 16: Urban ReLeaf Instagram page showing followers [M28]

The Urban ReLeaf Instagram page showcases more accessible and visual communications compared to LinkedIn, including reels and swipe graphics related to community engagement activities, which are tailored to reach local stakeholders and citizens.

In the first 28 months, the Instagram page has achieved 182 followers between months 4 and 28 of the project (see Figure 12).

The top post in terms of both highest reach and engagement rate is for World Cities Day (Reel) at 6.86%. This highlights the power of both the moving image and the Instagram model of pushing video or reels to generate interaction. The highest engagement rate of 10.26% among all posts is for the General Assembly Cascais (Reel) proving reels' ability to create meaningful interactions even with smaller audience reach.

Table 10: Top Performing Instagram Content (M4 – 28)

Instagram Post Title / Content	View / Impressions	Likes / Engagements / Interactions	Engagement Rate
DCC Photo Competition	2,480	1,420 and 27 engaged	1.90%
World Cities Day (Reel)	311	204 and 14 engaged	6.86%
DCC Launch Photos	343	280 and 16 engaged	5.7%
Weekly Cities Recap	480	356 and 15 engaged	4.21%

General Assembly Cascais (Reel)	212	117 and 12 engaged	10.26%
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Instagram Insights

- **Carousels and Reels** leverage high engagement rates and reels in particular generate interactive, engaging content.
- **Interactive Formats** such as competitions and recaps drive significant reach but could improve interaction with call-to-actions or polls.
- **Rotational Focus on Cities** ensures equal visibility, we will continue to follow a rotational content schedule highlighting one city per post per week or fortnight, however we need suitable content from partners to achieve this.

3.2.3 X / (Twitter)

Figure 17: Urban ReLeaf X account page showing followers [M25]

The Urban ReLeaf X channel has achieved 133 followers in the first 24 months (see Figure 13.). Analysis of X performance showed reasonable engagement rates and impressions, particularly for informative posts e.g., Website Launch. Interactive opportunities such as invitation to join the project at EURESFO, and partner collaborations e.g., Cascais also drove engagement.

However, since rebranding from Twitter to X in 2022, the platform has lost approximately 32.7 million users, reflecting a broader decline in user engagement. The project also concluded that maintaining a presence on the platform posed a communications risk due to X's increasingly controversial societal values.

Following a review of our social media presence, and a unanimous vote by all partners at the Urban ReLeaf General Assembly in February 2025, the consortium took the decision to archive our X presence. The X channel has been archived instead of deleting it to protect @releafcities' ID from being claimed by another party. This preservation approach maintains our digital identity while discontinuing active participation on the platform.

A summary of our top-performing posts is presented in Table 6, below. Unfortunately, we cannot provide analysis of metrics over time since this data is only available to premium account holders on the platform.

Table 11: Top Performing X Content (M4 – 25)

X Post Title / Content	View / Impressions	Likes / Engagements / Interactions	Engagement Rate
Launch of the project	4,480	146	2.88%
Website Launch	2,228	16	5.25%
EURESFO Marketplace post (come chat with us)	818	N/A	6.84%
Urban ReLeaf inspired poem premiered at CoP28	1350	26	N/A
Câmara Municipal de Cascais 'Proud to be involved of UR' post	1800	62	3.44%

3.3 Progress toward diversity and inclusion targets:

- Female participation (min. 50%): In progress. During campaign I in 2024, Cascais, Riga and Dundee collected profile data about their participants. The gender KPI was met in Cascais (58% female participation), and almost in Riga for campaign I (33%, or 4 females and 5 males, 3 others). The analysis of Dundee is ongoing.
- Participation from marginalised groups (30-40% target): In Progress. Target was met in Cascais (41.3% - defined as young adults, or, older adults, or

people with a low education level (basic education). The target was not met in Riga due to a high participation of highly educated, middle-aged participants. Remediation will be taken for the second campaign through targeted recruitment. Analysis of Dundee is ongoing.

- Drafted the [inclusivity statement](#) for the Urban ReLeaf website: Finished.
- Use of green and inclusive engagement guidelines: In progress
- Monitoring of inclusivity in pilot city activities: In progress in all six cities for campaign II in 2025, and completed for Cascais, Riga and Dundee for campaign I in 2024.
- Inclusivity statements for each city: Finished
- Consent forms tailored for Youth, Parents and Schools: Completed, templates for consent forms were drafted for the pilot cities.

AWAITING VALIDATION BY THE
EUROPEAN COMMISSION

4 Strategic updates to Engagement, Communications and Dissemination

Over the first two years, Urban ReLeaf's Engagement, Communication, and Dissemination (ECD) Plan has evolved in alignment with the project's goals, work package contributions, and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). Through monitoring, implementation feedback, stakeholder engagement, and adaptation to emerging strategic priorities, we have identified opportunities to refine the approach. This section outlines how the ECD strategy is being updated to meet our aims of increased visibility, stakeholder engagement, and dissemination of results as the project moves into its second half.

The four-phase ECD framework outlined in section 2 remains relevant, though adjustments have been made to reflect evolving contexts and practicalities. The adjustments and updates align with digital trends and the role of multimedia, online presence, community building and RRI in effective communication.

4.1 Lessons Learned and Strategic Insights (M1-28)

Insights gathered from implementation activities and partner engagement have informed an evolving approach, with both opportunities and challenges outlined below.

Strategic Application of the "Storytelling for Two" Framework

Analysis of our communications and dissemination activities, supported by engagement metrics, demonstrates that effective storytelling requires strategic curation of the "Storytelling for Two" framework's six 'W' guiding questions: Why, Who, What, When, Where, and How. Our review of over 30 articles and communications campaigns showed that the most compelling and shareable content focuses on two or three core elements that align with each story's purpose and target audience needs. This selective approach enables narrative development, emotional resonance and message clarity.

Urban ReLeaf's highest-performing content emphasises core combinations, such as "Who + Why" are relevant for expert interviews to build authority and urgency, "Where + How" for place-based innovations showcasing local relevance and practical methods, or "What + When" for milestone campaigns celebrating concrete achievements within meaningful timeframes. This audience-driven application of the framework continues to be monitored for its focus and effectiveness in creating narratives that actively invite audience engagement, sharing, and participation.

Key Implementation Insights

The following table summarises key insights from the application of the 'Storytelling for Two' framework and broader communication strategy. Each activity is supported by evidence from analytics, partner feedback, and campaign outcomes, highlighting

what has most effective for driving engagement, reach, and relevance across Urban ReLeaf ECD.

Table 12: Strategic Insights and Supporting Evidence

Description of strategy and activity	Supporting Evidence / Examples
The Hub and Spoke model (Urban ReLeaf core platforms amplified via partner networks and channels has proven effective for reach.	KPIs achieved
A centralised design and graphic service has improved consistency and partner capacity.	High volume of central design and branding requests by partners, positive feedback from consortium
City-specific storytelling resonates strongly with local audiences.	Analytics show 40% higher engagement rates for location-specific content compared to generic project updates
Multilingual materials expand accessibility and inclusivity.	Website analytics show increasing engagement from non-English speaking regions
Early policy engagement increases the relevance and uptake potential of pilot outcomes.	Analytics metrics show that Policy features with key leaders increase engagement
Ethics and alignment with platform values are critical for brand integrity.	Decision to decommission the X (formerly Twitter) account due to misalignment with Urban ReLeaf's values and ethics, and movement of target stakeholders
Engagement must be tailored per city to address variable social media performance.	Lower engagement in some cities without local social media presence requires targeted centralised support
'Storytelling for two' e.g., emotionally resonant, community-focused, topical and behind-the-scenes narratives increase interaction and sharing.	Emphasis on showcasing local stories, personalities, and cultural elements in each pilot city achieved 20-30% click-through rates vs. industry average 1-3%
Use of interactive content formats boosts user engagement and reach.	Analytics show polls, reels, carousels and competitions drive 60% higher interaction metrics than static posts

4.2 Updated Strategy, Audience & EDC Priorities (M28-48)

As Urban ReLeaf enters its maturity and scaling phase, the Engagement, Communication and Dissemination (ECD) strategy has been refined in response to evaluation findings, stakeholder feedback, and emerging strategic opportunities. While the four-phase framework remains relevant, the next 20 months demand a shift in emphasis, from foundational awareness-building to strategic dissemination, uptake, and post-project legacy. The following profiles outline how each strategic priority will evolve to ensure meaningful and measurable impact.

Awareness to Action

The early phases of Urban ReLeaf focused on building a strong foundation: establishing the project's visual identity, stakeholder networks, and pilot communication frameworks. With this groundwork in place, the emphasis now turns to translating pilot results into practical outcomes, aligned with upcoming activities e.g. the accelerator city programme, CoP forum, community and culture pop-up labs, and insights workshops. These include actionable insights, policy recommendations, and replicable methodologies tailored for uptake by replication.

Urban ReLeaf will launch a final series of high-impact **thematic campaigns** centred on co-creation, citizen empowerment, and nature-based solutions. These campaigns will be delivered through formats such as documentary-style videos, highlight reels, and human-centred stories curated directly from the pilot cities. These narratives are designed to connect emotionally, build trust, and drive interest from both public audiences and decision-makers.

Replication and Capacity Building

Urban ReLeaf's legacy depends not only on visibility but also on its ability to scale. As such, the project will support the growth of the **Accelerator Cities programme** by developing communications and storytelling assets for new cities. A **Toolkit, Technical, Impact Briefs** and a **Roadmap** will be disseminated to facilitate this replication.

The **Creativity and Culture Pop-Up Labs** are designed to commission artists, designers, and creative practitioners to work with communities in interpreting Urban ReLeaf data and environmental themes. These interventions will result in co-created outputs e.g., zines, crafting, exhibitions, or interactive installations. These initiatives offer technical and cultural pathways to wider adoption.

Dissemination will take a more strategic shape through a planned range of outputs, from **tailored policy briefs, peer-reviewed publications, technical reports, and insights workshops**. These outputs will be closely aligned with Urban ReLeaf's Key Exploitable Results (KERs), ensuring that communication supports real-world impact and exploitation opportunities. Campaigns will be structured around relevant policy moments and events to maximise relevance and visibility.

Content Legacy

The communication infrastructure is well established and so the focus shifts to sustainability and longer-term value. The project website will be refreshed to feature a curated repository of deliverables, datasets, and publications. Dedicated spaces for pilot city updates, replication guidance, and Community of Practice (CoP) resources will be expanded.

Accessibility and discoverability will be enhanced through search engine optimisation. A multimedia content library for cataloguing videos and reels is being prepared for launch in September 2025. These and additional measures for infographics are designed to ensure that Urban ReLeaf's outputs remain visible.

Audience-Centric Design

Communications in the final phase will be balanced between stakeholder needs and target audiences. This approach favours clarity, accessibility, and local relevance whilst at the same time meeting scientific rigour. Inclusive design principles will continue to underpin all outputs, from websites and toolkits to campaign videos and press materials.

Urban ReLeaf will continue to apply plain language standards, offer content in multiple languages, and provide formats suitable for all audiences. Special attention will be paid to the co-creation of localised narratives that reflect the lived experiences of participating communities. Inclusion metrics will be monitored to ensure equitable representation and engagement across stakeholder groups.

Targeted Influence

Moving beyond general awareness, the project will now concentrate its outreach on influential stakeholder groups that can enable policy and systemic uptake. This includes European, national, and local policymakers, professional associations, and international citizen science networks (see table 13).

Key stakeholder audiences for this next phase include:

Primary:

- Local and regional policymakers with decision-making authority over urban planning and environmental policy e.g. Local councillors with NAS and NAP responsibility
- Urban planners and technical staff responsible for implementing green infrastructure solutions e.g. Pilot and accelerator city planners, Architecture and Design Scotland (A&DS)
- Civil society organisations and community leaders actively engaged in environmental advocacy e.g. Friends of the Earth, Living Labs, Local climate and growing groups involved in Urban ReLeaf inclusive workshops, pilot and accelerator cities.
- Citizens and citizen scientists participating in environmental monitoring initiatives e.g. Urban ReLeaf pilot and accelerator city participants

Secondary:

- Fellow Horizon Europe projects and research networks working in complementary domains e.g. ECS Project, GALLANT, RIECS-Concept
- Replication cities interested in adopting Urban ReLeaf methodologies e.g. ICLEI network
- Academic researchers in urban studies, environmental science, and citizen science e.g. PEER network, ECSA,
- EU-level policy networks and standardisation bodies e.g. DG-Environment, EEA, SEPA

- Technology providers and innovation ecosystems in the environmental monitoring sector, these will be identified in our upcoming Design for Business sprints

This strategic focus ensures that Urban ReLeaf's final phase communications will effectively bridge research outcomes with practical implementation, supporting both immediate impact and long-term sustainability of project innovations.

4.2.1 EDC Plan and Dissemination Activities

Building on the strategic updates and stakeholders outlined above, the following Engagement, Dissemination and Communication) Plan outlines specific activities.

Table 13: EDC Plan and activities in Phase 3

Type	Activity / Output	Timeline	Target Audience	Format / Channel
Scientific Dissemination	Peer-reviewed journal articles (e.g. Frontiers in Sustainable Cities, Environmental Science & Policy)	M32–M46	Academia, Researchers	Open Access, Project website, ORCID and institutional repositories
Conferences	Presentations at ICLEI, ECSA 2025, EuroCities Forum	M30–M45	Municipalities, Civil Society	Presentations and papers, workshops, posters.
Insights Workshops	Replication & Uptake Workshops (1 per pilot city + 1 EU)	M34–M46	City planners, NGOs, Accelerator Cities	Hybrid in-person/online events
Accelerator Programme	Communications and storytelling, Support for 5+ cities	M36–M48	Local authorities and City Municipalities	Toolkits, Datasets, Sensors, Mentoring
Policy Dissemination	Thematic Policy Briefs (x4) aligned with EU Green Deal and Mission priorities	M31–M44	Policymakers, city networks	Briefs, mailings, LinkedIn & newsletters
CoP Engagement	WP5 Community of Practice forums and dissemination via ICLEI networks	M30–M48	City officials, Planners,	Presentations, articles, cross-linking
Cultural Engagement	Pop-Up Labs producing co-created outputs (zines, soundscapes, exhibitions)	M33–M46	Creative sector, Citizens, Cultural organisations	Exhibits, Social Media Local showcases, social media, documentation
Project Storytelling	Film and storytelling campaign	M38–M48	General public, media, advocacy networks	Videos, reels, interviews

4.3 Post-Project Sustainability

To ensure continued visibility, access, and relevance of Urban ReLeaf's core messages and results, the following measures will be implemented.

4.3.1 Long-term Communication Assets

Website Sustainability The project website (urbanreleaf.eu) will remain live for at least three years beyond the funding period. A final archival version will be produced, ensuring continued access to project deliverables, datasets, publications, and toolkits. Hosting may be transferred or integrated into an institutional or EU-level repository.

Social Media Continuity accounts (e.g., LinkedIn, Instagram) will continue to operate under a light-touch maintenance plan led by designated partner(s). Key campaign content, video stories, and citizen engagement highlights will be pinned or archived for long-term reference.

Transferable Branding and Templates All partners will continue to access finalised templates, toolkits, and brand assets to enable continued use in derivative or follow-up activities, maintaining Urban ReLeaf's visual and thematic coherence.

4.3.2 Knowledge Transfer

To maximise the long-term impact of the project's results and learnings we will explore knowledge transfer actions during our upcoming Design for Business sprints outlined in D6.3 Outreach, impact and Exploitation Report I.

5 Conclusion

This second iteration of the Urban ReLeaf Engagement, Communication, and Dissemination (ECD) Strategy restates the essential role of collaborative engagement across the consortium in amplifying the project visibility and impact. Urban ReLeaf adopts a hub-and-spoke communications model, where core project channels managed by UNIVDUN operate as central hubs, supported and extended by strategic partner channels (spokes) to maximise reach and relevance across local, national, and European contexts.

The strategy recognises that meaningful and inclusive engagement is at the heart of Urban ReLeaf's mission. Communication activities are aligned with project milestones and emerging insights and are focused on empowering local voices and co-creation efforts. The project continues to strengthen its presence across multiple stakeholder groups, including cities, policymakers, NGOs, citizens, and underrepresented communities.

A particularly successful strategic approach within this framework has been the adoption of "Storytelling for Two" a method that encourages locally relevant, action-oriented, and emotionally resonant narratives. This approach supports deeper connection with diverse audiences and encourages sharing across networks. Evidence from early implementation shows its effectiveness, with click-through rates ranging from 20–30% on relevant communications, significantly exceeding the general social media average of around 1–3%, this underscores the strategy of tailored and resonant storytelling in driving engagement and visibility.

WP6 led by UNIVDUN also supports an adaptive, service-oriented approach to visual identity and branding. The branding has matured to meet evolving needs, supporting everything from campaign insights to data visualisation, thematic illustrations, and the development of new graphical elements and iconography. This flexible, evolving visual strategy ensures consistency while enabling creativity and responsiveness to project developments and partner needs.

The updated ECD strategy builds on lessons learned during the first half of the project and provides a roadmap for deeper alignment across engagement, communication, and dissemination tasks. It supports Urban ReLeaf's thematic focus areas and continued collaboration between dissemination, exploitation, and impact activities.

WP6 will continue to refine and enhance its approach and will ensure that communication tools, channels, and narratives are inclusive, evidence-based, and aligned with Horizon Europe principles. The integration of strategic storytelling methods, including the use of reels and video, and monitoring of engagement will remain key to maintaining interaction and stakeholder interest. The strategy will guide the next phases of the project in strengthening stakeholder relationships, facilitating dissemination and knowledge transfer, supporting exploitation and enhancing public understanding of citizen-empowered data-gathering, nature-based solutions for urban design.

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Appendix 1

Social Media Graphics

Social media graphics for DCC photo competition

Selection of social media graphics -webinar promo, UR at EURESFO, CoP WG1 promo and Nature detectives

'Weekly Cities Series' recap slide along carousel post

World cities day reel

GA 2025 Reel

Dundee Launch Reel

Mannheim

Snapshot of article on website

Banner Design

Banner at New Year 2025 event

Images from 2025 New Years event

Images from 2025 New Years event

'Mannheim 2024 Campaign Insights' Poster

Mannheim Launches Tree Registry Campaign at the City's First Greening Fair

Poster and postcard design for App

Poster for New Years 2025 Event

Utrecht

'Utrecht 2024 Campaign Insights' Poster

Web banner designed for campaign launch

Image of workshop participation

Postcards for campaign launch

Images of Utrecht's Residents

Images of Utrecht's Residents

Digital flyer designed for campaign launch

Image of workshop participation

Stickers for campaign launch

Article on website

Cascais

'An Urban Park for the Future' campaign engagement

Cascais
Fully commitment to sustainable development, Cascais transforms urban greenspaces to improve the environment and quality of life for its residents.

In the campaign "A Future-Proof Urban Park," young city volunteers engage with citizens to share their thermal comfort and experiences in greenspaces via a web- or app-based survey, directly feeding into greenspace planning and policies. In 2025, Cascais expands its citizen science activity and engages city residents in measuring temperature and heat stress with mobile sensors. By identifying locations as heat spots, the campaign helps protect vulnerable groups from severe health risks and promotes a more resilient community.

2024 Campaign Insights

- 70 City volunteers
- >1400 Citizens engaged
- 58% of surveys completed by female participants
- 1498 Data points collected
- 7 Parks investigated
- The most comfortable greenspace: Quinta da Carreira Urban Park

Survey questions: "How do you feel about the temperature in this place?" and "At what time do you usually visit this place?"

'Cascais 2024 Campaign Insights' Poster

Snapshot of article on website

Banner designed for Cascais

'Cascais 2024 Campaign Data Insights' infographic

Banner en situ in Cascais Park

Cascais 'An Urban Park for the Future' Citizen Engagement

Riga

Urban ReLeaf

Riga

Riga's "Adopt a Sensor" campaign joins local residents to measure air pollution in collaboration with Riga authorities.

With 20 air quality sensors in place — spread across parks and outside homes, schools, and local NGOs — residents actively track $PM_{2.5}$ levels, comparing green and traffic-heavy areas. This citizen-based monitoring is not about data collection only; it empowers people and policy to better understand and take action to improve air quality in the city. In 2025, Riga additionally focuses on citizen-based temperature monitoring, raising awareness of urban heat islands and the role of greenspaces in mitigating their effects.

2024 Campaign Insights

- >40 Sign-ups to adopt a sensor
- >87,400 Data points collected
- 20 Sensors installed and operating
- 3 Urban policies informed

Riga city air quality improvement action program for 2020-2030
Riga action programme 2022-2027
Riga Greening plan 2027-2031

PurpleAir Riga Map

European Union

MR Research and Innovations

'Riga 2024 Campaign Insights' Poster

Sensor installation

Urban ReLeaf

'Adoptēt sensoru' panākumi: Rīga iesaista iedzīvotājus gaisa kvalitātes monitoringā

2024. gada 12. oktobris, plkst. 14:00

Ar šādu iniciatīvu, kas ir vērsta uz iedzīvotāju iesaisti, ir iespējams uzlabot gaisa kvalitāti un samazināt vides piesaistību. Šī gada beigās, kad sākās ziemeļrietumu vējš, Rīgā bija reģistrēti augstāki $PM_{2.5}$ līmeņi nekā iepriekšējās sezonās. Tāpēc ir svarīgi nodrošināt, lai gaisa kvalitātes monitoringa dati būtu pieejami iedzīvotājiem, lai viņi varētu pieņemt atbilstošas lēmumus.

Šī iniciatīva ir daļa no Rīgas pilsētas gaisa kvalitātes uzlabošanas programmas, kas ir vērsta uz iedzīvotāju iesaisti un gaisa kvalitātes monitoringa uzlabošanu. Rīga ir viena no pirmajām Eiropas pilsētām, kas ir sākusis šādu iniciatīvu.

Ar šādu iniciatīvu, kas ir vērsta uz iedzīvotāju iesaisti, ir iespējams uzlabot gaisa kvalitāti un samazināt vides piesaistību. Šī gada beigās, kad sākās ziemeļrietumu vējš, Rīgā bija reģistrēti augstāki $PM_{2.5}$ līmeņi nekā iepriekšējās sezonās. Tāpēc ir svarīgi nodrošināt, lai gaisa kvalitātes monitoringa dati būtu pieejami iedzīvotājiem, lai viņi varētu pieņemt atbilstošas lēmumus.

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Snapshot of article on website

Image of workshop participation

Dundee

Image from CoP workshop at Dundee University

Volunteers with designed banner

Image from Dundee UR launch with design assets

'Dundee 2024 Campaign Insights' Poster

Signage design for campaign

Snapshot of article on website

A5 Card design

'Nature Detectives' poster design

Photo competition poster

Images from Dundee UR launch

